

Frequency of Wound Dehiscence in Emergency Laparotomy Incision

Shahnila khizar¹, Muhammad Bilal Chishti², and Muhammad Usman Rauf³

¹Doctor at FMH College of Medicine and Dentistry LAHORE

Email: shahnilakhizar2@gmail.com

²Doctor at FMH College of Medicine and Dentistry LAHORE

Email: bilalchishti1@gmail.com

³Doctor at Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur.

Email: usmanrauf14@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Objective: To determine frequency of wound dehiscence after laparotomy done in emergency.

Design & Duration: This is a prospective study of observational type. Study was started in July 2019 and completed in December 2019 comprising on six months duration.

Setting: This study was conducted in FMH College of medicine and dentistry Lahore.

Patients and Methods: patients operated in emergency department during study duration irrespective of age and gender was included in this study. Patients having any malignancy, immune-compromised or taking chemo or radiation therapy were not included in this study. Consent was taken from all cases in this study and permission was also taken from ethical committee. Patients were prepared before surgery and whole baseline and special investigations were done where indicated. Patients were operated for various indications through midline incision and closure of abdominal wall was done in same way using proline-1 continuous stitches in all cases. Demographic data like age, gender, duration of symptoms were noted and means, standard deviation were calculated.

Results: There were 100 male and 50 female cases out of total 150 cases. There were 30 cases between 15-25 years, 38 between 25-35 years, 44 between 36-45 years, 28 were between 45-55 years and 10 were above 55 years of age. Wound dehiscence found in 23 cases 15 male and 8 female cases. Causes of laparotomy were typhoid perforation in 40 cases, tuberculous perforation of intestines in 34 cases, perforated appendix in 26 cases and abdominal trauma in 50 cases.

Conclusion: Wound dehiscence is much common in our hospitals after emergency laparotomy where which is due to improper closure or increased infection rate in emergency leading to surgical site Infection and wound dehiscence.

Key Words: Wound dehiscence, laparotomy, emergency laparotomy, wound infection

INTRODUCTION

Perforation of intestine due to typhoid or T.B leading to peritonitis and is an indication for laparotomy on emergency bases. These patients should be operated immediately as mortality rate is

very high in peritonitis. Immediate fluid resuscitation, antibiotic coverage, decompression of stomach and urinary catheterization with input and output monitoring are initial steps to manage such patients. Another common indication of laparotomy is abdominal trauma, which is very common in our country due to high rate of road side accidents. In emergency wards infection rate is usually higher than elective operation theaters due to 24 hours working o.t and infected cases are frequently operated here so in such conditions wound infections are common in laparotomy patients which can lead to wound dehiscence.

Patients and Methods: This is an observational prospective study completed in six months duration, Study was conducted in hospital attached to FMH college of medicine and dentistry Lahore. It is a tertiary care hospital with 24 hours working emergency department in which many surgeries are done on daily bases. Patients operated in emergency department during study duration irrespective of age and gender was included in this study. Patients having any malignancy, immune-compromised or taking chemo or radiation therapy were not included in this study. Consent was taken from all cases in this study and permission was also taken from ethical committee. Patients were prepared before surgery and whole baseline and special investigations were done where indicated. Patients were operated for various indications through midline incision and closure of abdominal wall was done in same way using proline-1 continuous stitches in all cases. Demographic data like age, gender, duration of symptoms were noted and means, standard deviation were calculated. Data was analyzed using SPSS software and presented in tabular form and graphs.

Results: There were 100(66.7%) male and 50(33.3%) female cases out of total 150 cases. There were 30(20%) cases between 15-25 years, 38(25.3%) between 25-35 years, 44(29.3%) between 36-45 years, 28(18.7%) were between 45-55 years and 10(6.7%) were above 55 years of age. Wound dehiscence found in 23(15.3%) cases 15(10%) male and 8(5.3%) female cases. Causes of

laparotomy were typhoid perforation in 40(26.7%) cases, tuberculous perforation of intestines in

34(22.7%) cases, perforated appendix in 26(17.3%) cases and abdominal trauma in 50 cases.

DISCUSSION

Many studies have been done in this perspective and it was found that wound infection causing dehiscence is much common in our hospitals after laparotomy especially done in emergency wards. Perforation of intestine due to typhoid or T.B leading to peritonitis and is an indication for laparotomy on emergency bases. These patients should be operated immediately as mortality rate is very high in peritonitis. Immediate fluid resuscitation, antibiotic coverage, decompression of stomach and urinary catheterization with input and output monitoring are initial steps to manage such patients. This is an observational prospective study completed in six months duration, Study was conducted in hospital attached to FMH college of medicine and dentistry Lahore. It is a tertiary care hospital with 24 hours working emergency department in which many surgeries are done on daily bases. Patients operated in emergency department during study duration irrespective of

age and gender was included in this study. Patients having any malignancy, immune-compromised or taking chemo or radiation therapy were not included in this study. There were 100(66.7%) male and 50(33.3%) female cases out of total 150 cases. There were 30(20%) cases between 15-25 years, 38(25.3%) between 25-35 years, 44(29.3%) between 36-45 years, 28(18.7%) were between 45-55 years and 10(6.7%) were above 55 years of age. Wound dehiscence found in 23(15.3%) cases 15(10%) male and 8(5.3%) female cases. Another common indication of laparotomy is abdominal trauma, which is very common in our country due to high rate of road side accidents. In emergency wards infection rate is usually higher than elective operation theaters due to 24 hours working o.t and infected cases are frequently operated here so in such conditions wound infections are common in laparotomy patients which can lead to wound dehiscence. A study done in Faisalabad also concluded comparative results as we concluded.

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